

Small Jobs; Big Worries:
Insecurities of Gig Work in the Time of Pandemic

Babu P Remesh¹ & Tanya Chaudhary²

Abstract

This article highlights the insecurities associated with the gig work which have been amplified during the pandemic. It is shown that this new form of temporary work, based on technology-mediation, is characterized by inherent adverse terms for the workers. A crisis period like pandemic is found deepening the worker's worries, which emphatically underscores the need for strengthening regulatory measures to assure dignified work for gig workers.

Keywords: Gig Work, Gig Economy, Online-Platform, Labour standards

Introduction

¹Professor & Dean, School of Development Studies, Ambedkar University Delhi. Email: babu@aud.ac.in.

²Research Scholar, School of Development Studies, Ambedkar University Delhi.

Of late, globally, there has been a proliferation of gig economy jobs, and India is not an exception to this trend. Though there is no authentic statistics available on the quantum of gig work in India, available estimates suggest that around 15 million people are currently engaged in gig based temporary work (Tiwari et al., 2020). There are also growing apprehensions that gig economy jobs are essentially non-standard by nature, with deplorable levels of labour standards. In this backdrop, the present paper attempts to analyze the inherent and deepening insecurities of gig work and workers in India. A special effort is made to understand the impact of the pandemic in further deteriorating the quality of work in the gig economy.

Conceptualizing Gig Work

In gig economy, working options are mostly based on very short-term jobs called ‘gig jobs’, which are normally for a single professional engagement and/or for a brief stipulated time period. So, one of the defining features of the gig work is the abysmally shorter length/duration of the contract. The term ‘gig’ stands for a one-time arrangement between the service provider and the user (through a mediator) which may or may not guarantee a long-term engagement. Woodcock and Graham (2020) use the term ‘gig economy’ to refer to the “labour markets that are characterized by independent contracting that happens through, via, and on digital platforms”. As Harris (2017) points out: “All gigs are jobs. But not all jobs are gigs”, where the requirement of the job is according to the need of the firm, which offers the work. However, the very short duration is not the only feature that makes gig work distinct from conventional and ‘standard’ jobs. Actually, it is the mediation of technology that helps in linking the workers with their job-providing intermediaries (and eventually with actual

clients) is the most defining feature of gig economy. In other words, gig work can be seen as technology enabled/mediated short-term labour contracts.

Gig workers include a wide range of employees who are known by different nomenclatures such as: Temp-job workers; Sharing-economy workers; Collaborative economy workers; Workers employed with aggregators; Online-platform workers; Independent contractors; Contract-firm workers; On-call workers and so on. The most visible examples of gig workers in the Indian context are the drivers in application (app)-based cab services (e.g. Uber, Ola) and the delivery persons working with food delivery platforms (e.g. Zomato and Swiggy). There are many more examples such as delivery staff engaged in e-commerce (e.g. Amazon, Flipkart) and workers engaged in delivery of vegetables and grocery items. At present, the concentration of gig jobs is more in the metropolitan cities, though these jobs are quickly spreading to small towns. In urban areas, the influence of gig work has gained considerable momentum in the recent past. Accordingly, 'from buying groceries to writing computer codes', workers are available through app-based mediation.¹ The list of platform-mediated gig economy services can be extended to many other fields like online hospitality networks (e.g. Airbnb, Oyo Rooms) and online market places (e.g. Policy Bazaar) and so on.²

Essentially, the gig work is similar to freelancing work or part-time work of bygone days. But, one of the main distinctions between conventional freelancing and gig job is the presence mediating technology (e.g. app-based/technology-enabled platform³). It is the centrality of technology (Apps; ITES/Web-based intermediation) that defines the possibilities as well as inherent insecurities of work and workers in the gig economy.⁴ The software application provides a platform that brings the service to the service requesters through a functioning set of

workers. The intention is to provide an accessible, speedy and geographically broad ranged service to the consumers. It has given way to develop a market for aggregators who aggregates surplus of workers to provide a quick service to the consumers, where network between the service provider and the user is dissolved once the task is completed.

Based on the physical positioning of the workers, the gig work can be classified into two. The first set of gig workers are those who are engaged in *field-based gigs*. These workers are directly present in the field (e.g. food delivery executives or cab-drivers). In the second category, the workers are *remote gig workers* (e.g. tele-sales or tele-counselling persons). In terms of pooling of resources too, we can also broadly divide gig workers into two. The first category of workers is those who principally work by providing their efforts and skills (labour power) alone. The next set are those who also share their assets along with the labour power.⁵

Viewing Gig Work from Actors' Perspectives

Essentially, there are three actors in gig work, namely on-demand companies, service providers and customers. On-demand companies are essentially the platform owners, who do the matching between the actual employers (customers) and the actual workers (service providers). They are the entrepreneurs in gig business, though usually they prefer to use different nomenclatures such as aggregators; platform providers; app-owners; tech-corporates and so on.⁶ Service providers are the *de facto* workers, who are denied of their worker status by the aggregators. Usually, in service related documents they are termed as 'service providers' or as independent contractors. The third actor is the customer or client, who avails the services of the temp-

employees through the mediation services of the on-demand firms.

Gig work offers different sets of possibilities and constraints for different actors in the gig economy. From the view point of the aggregators, gig work has many advantages. Firstly, organization of gig jobs reduces the costs in many ways. After initial investment (fixed cost) the recurring costs of running the platform/application is minimal, compared to the unlimited returns that the aggregators receive (as commissions from the workers/service providers, who use the platform). Once the platform/application is put in place, the recruitment cost becomes very minimal. Besides this, in zero-hour contracts, the employers are not liable to provide minimum hours of employment. Such a situation provides considerable levels of ‘numerical flexibility’ to the employers, especially when a large pool of reserve army of labour is readily available in labour-surplus economies (like India). As the workers are roped in through instant/very short-term contracts, the companies are also free from long-term obligations towards the workers. In addition to that, gig work arrangements also help the aggregators to become *de facto* owners of the resources shared by the other actors. In such situations, we can see emergence of a new class of ‘capitalists without capital’!⁷ From the customers’ point of view, usually, gig economy offers many advantages including availability of services at competitive prices, standardized/assured quality of services, numerical flexibility and so on.

For the workers also, there are some advantages, which prompt them to engage in gig work. Gig work options provide many workers to access employment (or enter in the labour market), without any operating cost (or prior investment). As the aggregators/platforms provide employment opportunities, there is ease of finding work. There is certain degree of inherent flexibility

in the gig work options. Usually, the workers are free to work or quit the work, whenever they feel like. As there is no obligation to accept all the works offered to them, many workers find it as a convenient arrangement for flexibly engaging in the labour market. For some of the gig workers, gig options provide opportunities for converting their hobby as a source of supplementary income, whereas for some others gig-work is test-drive for a new job-experiment. The freedom to simultaneously work more than one platform is yet another attraction.⁸

Notwithstanding the above, there are reasons to believe that there are many demerits for gig work from the workers' perspective, which far-outweigh the merits mentioned above. Absence of employment-security is one of the major shortcomings of gig-work. On the one hand, there is no long-term assurance regarding the continuation of the job. On the other hand, even in the gig work option, there are uncertainties regarding an assured minimum level of work. Last minute rescheduling of work and cancellation of orders are quite common in gig-work options. Due to all these, the income from gig work is often irregular, inadequate and inconsistent.

As opposed to regular employees in other comparable sectors, gig workers are denied of many benefits including assured minimum wages, over time, unemployment allowance, and social protection, medical/maternity leaves, paid leaves, severance packages/retirement benefits and so on. Quite often these 'self-employed' workers are on a continuous struggle for 'self-exploitation'.

As many of these workers are often with some loan liabilities (and at times are in the clutches of micro finance and banking institutions, the gig workers are susceptible to burn out and do many hours of stressful work to make both the ends meet. For many of them, it is a struggle to move from one gig to another

on a continuous basis. All these suggest that gig works are often comparable with works in informal sector, which are characterized by acute levels of precariousness. The precarious conditions of the workers are inherently built into the algorithms of the apps as well as the hierarchical structure of these companies. For instance, the delivery personnel with a good customer rating will get a badge which would assure him more orders, or getting a minimum wage or reward in case of completion of targeted number of rides or delivery, where the order or ride for achieving the targeted number is not given so easily as per algorithms; or the geographical areas where delivery personnel who ride along in the area would get more orders. The fact that even with all these insecurities there are many workers who are willing to participate in gig economy itself is an indication of the overall deterioration of labour standards in this sector.

Usually, the aggregators or platform providers dominate in the collaborative partnership. This allows them in charging exorbitant commissions (which even go up to 20-25%) and fixing abysmally low amounts as service charges for their on-call workers. The firms can also control the workers by monitoring and regulating their telephonic interactions. In certain gig-working arrangements, the workers are restricted from working with alternative platforms. At times, there are stipulations that workers need to fulfil a minimum number of tasks (target) to be eligible for certain benefits. In certain other cases the workers need to follow some of the guidelines and stipulations of the collaborating firm/brand (e.g. wearing uniforms, displaying signage and logo; using delivery bags of company; using of certain apps etc.)

Yet another disadvantage from the worker's point of view is the absence of socialization and threats to collectivity. As the workers are all scattered and disorganized by design, it is difficult

to organize the gig employees. Normally, gig workers are individually connected, circulating/floating personnel and often find themselves as ‘self-isolated’, as they may not be getting any chances to frequently meet or socialize with their fellow-workers.

Inherent Insecurities in Gig Work

Denial of ‘workers’ status to the employees has been a major issue concerning gig work in the recent past. By calling the workers by different nomenclatures such as ‘delivery partners’, ‘independent contractors’ and ‘aggregators’, the employers (aggregators) are found shirking their responsibilities towards workers.⁹ As the workers are not recognized as employees¹⁰, there is a difficulty in establishing employer-employee relationship and this absence of worker status, push out from the protective cover of the labour legislations and welfare measures, which are accessible to many other workers in the service economy.¹¹ Due to absence of legislative protection, lower labour standards and precarious nature of work become characteristic features of labour in gig economy.

Of the many inherent insecurities of gig work, the most important is the platform dependency, which is in-built in gig work. As accessing work is strictly routed through the platform, owned by the aggregator, the free and active engagements of workers are restricted by the mediators and technology.¹²

Collaboration in gig-work is basically a collaboration between unequal partners, as the aggregators/platform providers enjoy greater freedom in terms of imposing conditions of work, controls and directives, which the ‘workers’ have to treat *fait accompli*. Besides this, the price and incentive structures and the larger workplace practices are also normally decided and dictated by the employers.

In labour-surplus countries like India, gig work has yet another underlying dilemma. In western economies, the gig-based freelancing usually provides income-supplementing and part-time working opportunities for seekers of temporary-jobs.¹³ In lesser developed countries, gig work often becomes full time profession for those who fail to get a tenure-secure employment. Such situations often lead to a scenario where gig works are predominantly occupied by workers, who are permanently-temporary!

Deepening Insecurities during the Pandemic

Though there is no consolidated estimate of jobs lost during pandemic in gig work, it is now widely acknowledged and understood that the unexpected advent of pandemic and the lockdown that followed¹⁴ resulted in considerable job-losses and/or short-term unemployment for many workers in the gig-economy. As per reports, in the first few months of the lockdown, the ride-hailing giant Uber registered a job-loss of about 25%, while in Ola cabs 1400 persons lost their jobs. Food delivery collaborators like Swiggy, Zomato had also fired many of their delivery partners as the firms had to scale down to operate in pandemic (Bhargava 2020).¹⁵

When the food delivery services and cab-services were soon included as permitted activities during the initial phases of relaxation of lockdown restrictions, many of these workers had to risk their own lives (and those of their family members), to retain their jobs. Many gig workers had to carry on with their field-based work, without any personal protective equipment (PPE) kits or safety measures. As social distancing was not feasible in most of the cases, the occupation-related health risks was at its maximum. For delivery persons, payment in cash (on delivery) itself was a

major health risk (till payment through digital mode became the accepted norm). During this period, many of these workers also had to face customer abuse/ill-treatment, as these workers were viewed as potential carriers of the virus,¹⁶ despite their status as ‘essential workers’. In many cases, neighborhoods and housing societies not only restricted their entry but also harassed them during the lockdown while they were attending to their duties. Here, their identity as ‘blue collar workers’ has become the reason for the humiliation that they had to face. Along with this social stigma, incidents of harassment by police at check posts and attacking of food-delivery persons for money and food were also reported.¹⁷

Though drivers and delivery partners were directed by the aggregators to follow health-safety norms for themselves and their customers, often the cost and onus of having these safety measures (PPE kits¹⁸, sanitizers; soaps – disinfectants, plastic shields between passengers and driver in cabs and so on) were shifted to the workers.

Acute income-loss was another issue faced by gig workers during the pandemic.¹⁹ If we take the case of cab-services, lockdown implied considerable decline in the work of drivers engaged in ride-hailing services such as Uber/Ola. Closure of airports, stoppage of public transport, suspension of train services, closure of shops and establishments and so on cumulatively effected a huge decline in the demand for the services of these drivers, in the initial few months which were characterized by temporary unemployment or acute levels of under employment to majority of gig workers in the service sector.

The costs incurred by workers also increased considerably during the period, as the workers had to incur additional costs for precautionary measures (e.g. soaps; sanitizing material; healthcare related expenses). At the same time, the fuel

costs also were on the increase. In addition to these, there has been an overall increase in the workload and work-related stress. The number of working hours increased for all gig workers, as they had to spend more time on ensuring health and hygiene related norms (e.g. disinfecting the vehicles; use of Aarogya Setu App; temperature checks and covid tests²⁰).

Notwithstanding these increase in costs and efforts of the gig-workers, there was no revision in the per gig/per order charges paid to the workers by the aggregators. Nor was there any reduction in the commission rates charged by the platform owners (which were often as high as 20 to 25%).²¹.

As platform-based activities require only minimal running cost, there is lot of scope for reducing the commissions. But none of the aggregators were implementing such reduction in commissions. Rather, there has been a visible trend among the aggregators to shift their minimum responsibilities (related to social security) towards the customers.

The relief-measures provided by firms were often limited to a public statement in media or sending messages to workers about hygiene and sanitization. Many of the platform giants had openly approached the customers seeking their help in financing their workers during the time of pandemic.²² Medappa and Taduri (2020) explain how the aggregators were using 'crowdfunding' as an option to shift their responsibility of providing basic social security for their workers (or 'partners' as they are called!). While doing so, adjectives like 'heroes' or 'warriors' were effectively used.

There are reports that though these crowd-funding initiatives like Uber Care Driver Fund and Ola Care gathered huge amounts, only a small percentage of these resources reached the needy gig workers. Lalvani and Sitharaman (2020) point out that the insurance which Swiggy provided to the workers in case they

test COVID-19 positive was not able to provide them adequate assurance. Many factors are believed to have affected the efficacy of these schemes including faulty/rigid definition of beneficiaries, lack of transparency, lack of awareness and so on. In certain cases, the stipulation of self-reporting by the gig workers to avail the assured social security benefits itself affected the performance of the welfare measure. As self-reporting was immediately followed by a disconnection from the app (in the larger interest of customer safety), many gig workers opted for non-reporting even if they are infected by the virus. Such situations were found to further endanger and worsen the working environment of the gig workers.

The aggregators were also found effectively utilizing the pandemic and lockdown as a possibility for expanding the business in new directions and for seeking tax exemptions. There has also been attempts to shift some of the labour related responsibilities to government. From the government side also, though food-app based delivery workers were considered as ‘essential workers’ during difficult times, these workers were not given priority while providing social security assistance.²³

In the absence of effective protective measures, from both the aggregators and the state, often the get into debt-traps for meeting their daily expenses, equal monthly instalments (EMIs) and other contingency expenses during a pandemic-stricken period. Accordingly, more and more gig workers are now finding themselves as clients to informal money lenders and micro financing organizations, which further add to their vulnerabilities and insecurities.²⁴

Conclusion

The COVID-19 pandemic certainly used the digital platforms and Information and Communications Technologies (ICTs) for

sustaining citizens as the time of lockdown through excessive use of digital payments, digital work, digital governance and policing and even digital healthcare through online suggestive consultations. Although these services were heavily disposed towards upper- and middle-class population, the platforms also played an essential role in distribution of ration to migrant workers or flow of information within and between the communities of workers. This axiomatic relationship between platform economy and state was visible in the times of crisis in big cities²⁵ and hence is suggestive of the fact that platform economy has become a fundamental part of urban lives in metropolitan cities. Notwithstanding this, it is evident from the foregoing discussions that currently, there are many decent work deficits in the gig work options. The workers are often forced to work with abysmally lower labour standards, without any system for redressal²⁶, healthy socialization/collectivization or social dialogue. With no regulatory mechanism in place for workers to address their issues concerning work and livelihoods, the growth of digital economy does not offer an all-inclusive story of development.

Presence of no authority where a worker or the ‘dispensable partner’ (Shipra and Behera, 2020) could go to address the conditions of work, unfair termination or even complaint against the consumer makes the systematic structure of platform work precarious. The ultimate reliance on customer ratings to assess and evaluate workers’ income (through performative rewards and biases of algorithm to allocate more work) should be reduced to a balance between customer satisfaction and workers’ dignity. The worker should be given appropriate autonomy to take decision on behalf of company in case of customer dissatisfaction through refunds, which could be verified by a digital form or other means on a mobile-based application. Besides an apprehensive training to the workers to

deal with plausible conditions of dissatisfaction, conflict and threat would ensure both customer and worker's welfare. The consideration of human capacities needs to be fed into the algorithm of these apps, which would then not lead to a disparaging working conditions and hence make companies accountable for workers' income and social security.

On the whole, the foregoing discussion emphatically underscores that strengthening regulatory measures to assure dignified jobs for workers in the gig economy is an important requirement. Inclusion of gig workers in the recently passed Social Security Code, 2020²⁷, and a recent judgement in the UK's Supreme Court²⁸, approving 'worker' status to the Uber drivers and so on are some encouraging recent developments in this direction. Notwithstanding these, there is a long way to go for promoting fair labour standards in the gig economy.

References

- Appadurai, A. 2012. The Spirit of Calculation. *The Cambridge Journal of Anthropology*, 30(1): 3–17.
- Athique, A and Parthsarthy, V. (eds.). 2020. *Platform Capitalism in India*. Switzerland: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Bhargava, Y. 2020. Now, Swiggy, to lay off 1100 employees. *The Hindu*, May 18, 2020. Available at: <https://www.thehindu.com/business/now-swiggy-to-lay-off-1100-employees/article31613220.ece>. Accessed on April 20, 2021.
- Chakravarti, A. 2020. Covid19 lockdown: Online delivery of food items is essential service but don't rely on it for your dinner". *India Today*, 25 March, 2020. Available at: <https://www.indiatoday.in/technology/news/story/covid19-lockdown-online-delivery-of-food-items-is-essential-service-but-don-t-rely-on-it-for-your-dinner-1659490-2020-03-25>. Accessed on April 12, 2021.
- Dash, S. 2021. 'Uber loses a major case in UK which rules its drivers are workers, a ruling that could impact the ride-hailing giant everywhere including India', *Business Insider*, February 19, 2021. Available at: <https://www.businessinsider.in/business/news/uber-loses-a-major-case-in-uk-which-rules-its-drivers-are-workers-a-ruling-that-could-impact-the-ride-hailing-giant-everywhere-including->

doi:

- [india/articleshows/81108812.cms#:~:text=The%20UK%20Supreme%20Court%20ruled,workers%2C%20not%20gig%20economy%20workers.&text=This%20ruling%20could%20impact%20all,mini%20entrepreneurs%20or%20independent%20contractors.](https://india.articleshows/81108812.cms#:~:text=The%20UK%20Supreme%20Court%20ruled,workers%2C%20not%20gig%20economy%20workers.&text=This%20ruling%20could%20impact%20all,mini%20entrepreneurs%20or%20independent%20contractors.) Accessed on April 10, 2021.
- Harris, Kristen. 2017. Job vs. Gig: What's the Difference and Why It Matters. Available at: <https://www.portfoliocreative.com/blog/2017/1/18/job-vs-gig-whats-the-difference-and-why-it-matters>. Accessed on April 20, 2021.
- Lalvani, S and Seetharaman, B. 2020. The Personal and Social Risks That India's Food Delivery Workers Are Taking During COVID-19. *The Wire*, Available at: <https://thewire.in/business/covid-19-food-delivery-workers>. Accessed on April 3, 2021.
- Medappa, K. 2021. 'Labour Wrongs'. *The Indian Express*. 23 March, 2021.
- Medappa, K. and Taduri, P. 2020. 'By crowdfunding benefits for embattled workers, app-based services are evading their own obligations' *The Scroll*, 22 April 2020. Available at: <https://scroll.in/article/959766/by-crowdfunding-benefits-for-embattled-workers-app-based-services-are-evading-their-own-obligations>. Accessed on 23 April, 2021.
- Mehrotra, S and Sarkar, K. 2021. Social Security Code, 2020 and Rules: A critique. *Economic and Political Weekly*. 56(12). Available at: <https://epw.in/journal/2021/12/commentary/social-security-code-2020-and-rules.html>. Accessed on June 16, 2021.
- Shipra and Behera, M. 2020. Gig Work and Platforms during the COVID-19 Pandemic in India. *Economic and Political Weekly*, 55(45) Available at: <https://epw.in/engage/article/gig-work-and-platforms-during-covid-19-pandemic>. Accessed on June 16, 2021.
- Srnicek, N. 2017. *Platform Capitalism*. Cambridge: Polity.
- Surie, A. 2020. Pandemic Exposure: 'Platform' Infrastructure in Public Use in India', 17 August, 2020. Available at: <https://www.compas.ox.ac.uk/2020/pandemic-exposure-platform-infrastructure-in-public-use/>. Accessed on April 20, 2021.
- Tiwari, S., Ram, R.S. and Roy, S. 2020. 'Three Gigs, Three Men, Three Stories'. *The Times of India*, February 12, 2020. Available at: <https://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/india/what-it-is-like-to-work-in-a-gig-economy-job/articleshows/69371217.cms>. Accessed on April 18, 2021.
- Woodcock, J., and Graham, M. 2019. *The Gig Economy*. London: Polity Press.

Notes

¹ Currently, there are many app-based services available in matching the customers with a wide range of workers such as home cleaners; home tutors; electricians; plumbers; yoga teachers; dog Trainers/dog walkers; care workers; tele-sales

persons; content writers; translators; editors; accountants; Tele-Medicine consultants; counsellors, to name a few.

² The discussions around gig work and workers schemed in this paper gives more attention on the app-based cab-drivers and food delivery executives, who are the most visible gig workers in our contemporary urban space.

³ Athique and Parthasarthy (2020) view that the platforms are market system instead of simple technical system. Borrowing from Appadurai (2012) and Srnicek (2017) the authors use the term 'platform-capitalism' to ensconce and illustrate that how platforms are normalized as controlling our social, economic and cultural ambits of life.

⁴ With the advent of gig work in a big way, distinction between short-term freelancing and gig work is becoming blurred. It seems as if the world of freelancing is transforming with technological intervention.

⁵ For instance, there can be cases where cabs in the ride-hailing services are owned by drivers; or owners who have pooled their rooms to an accommodation where service aggregators are doubling as workers in their own premises.

⁶ Assuming other names than that of employer or entrepreneur is viewed as a circumvention strategy followed by these firms, to avoid direct responsibilities towards workers.

⁷ Examples for this include food delivery aggregators like Swiggy; Zomato enjoying control over hundreds of restaurants (even without having a single restaurant of their own) and cab and lodging aggregators like Uber, Ola and Oyo rooms handling cars and rooms pooled by their collaborating partners.

⁸ For instance, we can see many cab-drivers working simultaneously with Uber and Ola.

⁹ This is quite similar to the case of Anganwadi workers and scheme workers, who are paid with a honorarium (instead of wages/salaries) as their work is considered as 'honorary work'!

¹⁰ The identification of workers as 'partners' was one of the main reasons that enabled platform based companies to elude legislative frameworks which ensures and safeguards workers' welfare and income security. Besides, this also facilitated the companies to get

away with the cost of ownership of assets and maintenance of assets used in the job, such as fuel costs, EMI payments etc. The blurring of the labour's place in the present capitalist production process is because of constant push to evade the employer-employee relationship which thrives on the superficial idea of 'flexibility' and undermines the dangerously long hours, lack of social security, low pay, digital surveillance and unfair dismissal (Medappa 2021)

¹¹ Accordingly, quite often, occupation related accidents (e.g. road accidents) are not compensated and issues like insecurities during workplace (e.g. sexual harassment faced by a female beautician, who is on gig work) are not adequately addressed by the actual employers.

¹² From a Marxian perspective, this can be seen as alienation of labour from the means of production!

¹³ In western-economies many people consider gig-based freelancing as an avenue for effectively utilising a few hours in a flexible manner for some additional income (e.g. Students working with fast-food chains such as Mc Donald's and those who engage in dog walking, snow-shoveling and so on)

¹⁴ The nationwide lockdown was announced from 24 March, 2020. Subsequently, lockdown was relaxed on 1st June 2020.

¹⁵ During the initial few months since the lockdown, there was considerable dip in the demand in the field of food delivery services, which deepened the hardships and worries of thousands of youngsters who were working in food delivery platforms such as Zomato and Swiggy.

¹⁶ Chakravarti 2020 observes that workers from food and grocery delivery services such as Zomato, Swiggy, Big basket which delivered essential goods were not only facing threat to their health but were also harassed by authorities and residents of neighborhoods.

¹⁷ During the days of panic and massive exodus of migrants towards their native places, there have been a few incidents where food delivery persons were attacked and their food packets are taken away.

¹⁸ At times, though these health safety material were provided by employers, the workers had to travel long-distances to access these. One of the major demands in the protest done by Indian Federation of app-Based Transport workers (IFAT) based in Hyderabad in June 2020 was the distribution of PPE kits and masks at accessible places.

¹⁹ As per reports, during the lockdown, with diminished orders in early days of lockdown, several workers in platform companies were left without even a basic level income, to sustain their families and meet expenses like payment of EMI on loans.

²⁰ Many cab-drivers had to do covid test multiple times, to follow the norms set by their employers or in certain cases, the government.

²¹ One of the major demands of the protest of app-based cab-drivers (organized by IFAT in Hyderabad) was to reduce the commission rates. Similarly, the protest staged by All India Gig Worker Union in NOIDA in September 2021 was to increase the service charges per order for food delivery executives.

²² Companies like Zomato, Uber and Ola had gone for such crowdfunding options. Interestingly, for these companies, supporting their own workers was financially non-viable!

²³ For instance, immediately after the lockdown a strike was organized by United Food Delivery Partners Union basically to fight for inclusion of food delivery executives (in relief measures)

²⁴ In the time of pandemic, many cab-drivers working with ride-hailing aggregators such as Uber and Ola had to seek and work in other jobs (under precarious conditions) or had to incur debts at high interest rates to pay the EMI of their cars. Some of them also sold/mortgaged their vehicles to money lenders and returned to their villages.

²⁵ In case of Delhi where a major section of workers employed by informal sector of the city were unemployed and many of them became devoid of shelter as well. Shutting down of various industries, informal street work, markets had left millions of workers to be stranded. The primary objective of Delhi government became to feed these workers and hence it tied up

with Swiggy, where the meals were prepared in government kitchen while food was distributed by delivery personnel. On an average 200,000 meals were distributed per day (Surie 2020). Later various other platform companies collaborated with Delhi government to distribute dry ration to people as well

²⁶ There is no redressal systems for the gig workers to resort to when they are denied of eligible payments by the aggregators or when they are met with issues such as customer abuse. A recent incident in Bangalore, in which a food delivery boy was beaten and ill-treated by a customer had once again highlighted of redressal mechanism for gig workers. The Bangalore incident suggests that even a formal SOS training to the workers will prove beneficial for both the consumers and the workers,

²⁷ As part of this Code on Social Security, a Gig Workers' Welfare Fund is also proposed which will be run charging 2 per cent on the turnover of the companies (as part of CoSS). Although the acknowledgement of gig work in CoSS seems a positive turn, there are many complexities involved when it comes to the implementation of this code, which needs to be realised through cooperative efforts from both the central and state governments (Mehrotra and Sarkar 2021)

²⁸ In 2021, February, Uber lost a major case in U. K's Supreme Court, with unanimous ruling pointing out that ride hailing giant's drivers are workers and not partners (Dash 2021).